

Synthesis of (3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-syrylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone via 1,3-dipolar Cycloaddition of Furfuraldehyde Nitron with Chalcone and Exploration of its Biological Activities

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Abstract— 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition is an extremely versatile route for synthesising five-membered heterocycles. Using heterocyclic nitron and Cinnamaldehyde chalcone through 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions reported here, for the synthesis of novel isoxazolidine derivatives. A novel heterocyclic compound, 3-(furan-2-y)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidine-5-yl)(phenyl)methanones are synthesized, characterized, and further subjected to antibacterial activity. The FT-IR, UV, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra reveals the structural elucidation of newly synthesised heterocyclic compound namely isoxazolidine. The powder XRD technique has been performed to examine the further confirmation of the synthesised new isoxazolidine derivative. The synthesised isoxazolidines are biologically active towards Gram negative Escherichia coli, Klebsiella oxytoca and Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Gram positive Staphylococcus aureus and Staphylococcus epidermidis and reported.

Keywords— Heterocyclic compounds, Microwave-assisted 1,3- Cycloaddition, Nitron.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many methods for synthesizing heterocyclic compounds have been published in the last few years.¹ Numerous researchers have been inspired to investigate the creation of sustainable methods for obtaining heterocyclic due to their extensive therapeutic profile.² The current stage in the evolution of organic chemistry and closely related fields of biology has been identified by considerable research into biologically active chemicals found in plants and animals that play vital roles in life. Furthermore, several well-known applications of heterocyclic compounds include the production of dyes, synthetic resins, synthetic rubbers, and other vital materials.³ Furfuraldehyde was first manufactured industrially from rice husks in 1840, after drying, combining with sodium chloride, and adding 10% H₂SO₄ and purified water.⁴ Other researchers synthesized it from rice straw.⁵ The researchers successfully synthesized furfuraldehyde from xylose sugar.^{6,7} Other researchers created furfuraldehyde from epic rap of wild mango. The researchers created furfuraldehyde from bagasse.⁸ According to the preceding research, furfural is a low-cost precursor that has been used to synthesize a wide range of heterocyclic compounds. Among the known furfural reactions that produce heterocyclic compounds.⁹

Cycloaddition technique are thought to be among the most prevalent, diverse, and advantageous kinds of chemical reactions. Because of its atom economy, stereo specificity, and ability to create complex molecules, cycloaddition is a significant chemical process. This is without a doubt the most often used

dipole nitrene in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition (1,3-DC). 1,3-DC reactions play a major role in the production of heteroatom-containing cycloadduct with the maximum atomic economy.¹⁰⁻¹³ Here, we publish the spectrum data and present the biological activity and synthesis of numerous new substituted isoxazolidines. Due to its stability and lack of need for in situ manufacturing, nitrene is one of the dipoles used in the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction the most frequently. Multiple heterocyclic rings of different diameters are produced by the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrenes with different dipolarophiles. These heterocycles are used in natural products, bioactive substances, and pharmaceuticals in a variety of ways. The nitrenes that create heterocyclic rings through cycloaddition with different substrates are the subject of this report.¹⁴ Nitrenes can be easily synthesized using the related nitro compound and aldehyde. An alternative method involves isolating the phenyl hydroxylamine that is created when the nitro molecule is reduced, and then reacting it with the aldehyde.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

A. PREPARATION

All of the chemicals (Zn powder, furfuraldehyde, nitrobenzene, ammonium chloride, acetophenone, sodium hydroxide pellets, and ethanol) are of reagent-grade quality and don't require additional distillation. The refluxing process was used to create the furfuraldehyde nitrene. It has persisted for extended periods of time. During TLC, the furfuraldehyde nitrene reactions have been seen using silica gel plates. The process of stirring and recrystallizing was used to create chalcone. Chalcone and nitrene that have been produced are more stable over time. Novel isoxazolidine compounds are synthesized by the usual procedure. CDCl₃ was utilized as a solvent at 400 MHz and TMS (diluted tetramethylsilane) was employed as an internal standard. The ¹H NMR spectra data were recorded using Bruker NMR spectra. The ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at 100 MHz using the identical apparatus, and the coupling constant (J) is displayed in Hz.

B. SYNTHESIS OF PHENYLHYDROXYLAMINE

A conical flask has been inserted, complete with a mechanical stirrer and thermometer. Then, add the base substances ammonium chloride (10g) in 320 ml of water and 16.6 ml of nitrobenzene to the container and well mix. In addition to the mixture, add 23.6 g of Zn powder (90% purity) for 15 minutes. The amount of addition could result in a rapid increase in temperature to 60°-65°C. Then, continue stirring for another 15 minutes until the temperature begins to drop. Zinc oxide is removed from the heated reaction mixture by Wash the pump with 100 milliliters of hot water after filtering it. Place the leftovers in the conical flask, wet through the combination with 60 g of common salt, and cool it in an ice-cold bath for at least an hour to ensure the greatest crystallization of the desired result. The pale-yellow phenyl hydroxylamine crystals were next suction-filtered and thoroughly drained.

C. SYNTHESIS OF CHALCONE((4E)-1,5-DIPHENYL-2,4-DIEN-1-ONE)

20 ml of ethanol are used to dissolve 7 ml of cinnamaldehyde and 6 ml of acetophenone. This solution was mixed with 20 grams of equimolar NaOH and the pellets at the same time. Then, for forty minutes, the reaction mixture was stirred. Additional ethanol was added after the mixture had been stirred for 40 minutes at 40⁰C. After cooling, cold water was added to dilute it. The chalcone is made using the procedure described above.

D. CYCLOADDITION REACTION OF α -FURFURAL ARYL-N-ARYL NITRONE WITH 1,5-DIPHENYLPENTA-2,4-DIEN-1-ONE

Scheme I for refluxing a mixture of α -Furfural aryl-N-aryl nitrone (**1**) and Cinnamaldehyde Chalcone (**2**) in 50ml of toluene for the designated amount of time. The solvent was extracted at decreased pressure once the reaction was complete, as shown by TLC, and the product 3-(furan-2-y)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidine-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone (**3**) was recrystallized from petroleum ether. (**Scheme I**)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present investigation, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction derived from furfuraldehyde nitrone and cinnamaldehyde chalcone have been reported. It is used to develop the synthesis of new set of isoxazolidine. The newly synthesized isoxazolidine is known as 3-(furan-2-y)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidine-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone. We have approach a procedure that followed the reflux method to synthesis the nitrone in ethanol.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ Nitrones are constants that are frequently used as dipoles in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition. Here, furfuraldehyde nitrone is the preferred dipole. Cinnamaldehyde chalcone was made using the stirring and recrystallization method. The Cinnamaldehyde chalcone is known as 1,5-diphenylpenta-2,4-dien-1-one. Here, cinnamaldehyde chalcone has chosen as a dipolarophile. The freshly prepared Cinnamaldehyde Chalcone and furfuraldehyde nitrone were refluxed for 15 to 18 hours in the presence of toluene to form a mixture, and the TLC method was used to determine the intervals between the reaction conditions. Before recrystallization, isoxazolidine is purified using column chromatography with an eluent of ethyl acetate and pet ether. The 5-membered substituted isoxazolidine is formed by combining furfuraldehyde nitrone and substituted cinnamaldehyde chalcone.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of isoxazolidine

However, when dipolarophile is cycloadditionally added as various chalcone types, the corresponding cycloadduct is a mixture of 3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone. A silica gel column was used to separate the main products of substituted isoxazolidine derivatives 3(a-f) using a suitable eluent mixture of petroleum ether. The Product obtained was characterized by means of the ^1H and ^{13}C spectroscopic technique. The scope and applicability of this synthetic process are illustrated using furfuraldehyde nitronium ion and substituted cinnamaldehyde chalcone. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C were used to structurally characterize each of the synthesized isoxazolidines. Table 2 provides a summary of these novel 3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone antibacterial activity after their bacterial activity was assessed in agar media. Scheme 1 illustrates the synthesis of isoxazolidine.

Figure 1: UV-Visible spectra of the synthesized novel isoxazolidine 3.

All cyclo adduct structures were found by spectroscopic investigation of the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra. The ^1H NMR spectra show signals at 5.73 (1H, dd), 5.26 (1H, d), 4.73 (1H, d), and 3.39 (1H, ddd), indicating the formation of 3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidine-5-yl(phenyl)methanone. UV absorbance at 290 nm confirms the isoxazolidine ring structure. Figure 2 shows the FT-IR spectra. The C=O stretching vibration was found to be responsible for the peak at 1612 cm^{-1} . The peaks represent the C=C bending vibration at around 690 cm^{-1} . These results indicate the formation of the isoxazolidine ring system through the synthesis of **3**.

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of the synthesized novel isoxazolidine 3.

Figure 3: PXRD of the synthesized novel isoxazolidine 3.

PXRD was utilized to investigate the produced compounds. A common analytical method for determining the crystalline structure, content, and physical characteristics of materials in powdered form is called powder X-ray diffraction, or PXRD. The XRD powder used to analyze the isoxazolidine compound's state. The PXRD pattern of 3 shows peaks at $d=2.82$, 2.00 , and 1.63 , with angle regions at $2\theta=31.61$, 45.26 , and 56.33 , respectively. The condition of the isoxazolidine is amorphous or powder, which is confirmed by the XRD technique.

TABLE I

COMPOUND	R	TIME (h)	YIELD (%)
3a	4-NO ₂	18	87
3b	2-CH ₃	20	90
3c	2-F	16	85
3d	4-Cl	20	90
3e	2-Br,4-Cl	18	87
3f	4-OH,2-OCH ₃	17	86

Table 1: Synthesis of novel isoxazolidine using different types of dipolarophiles

A. ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

The disk diffusion method is one of the most adaptable susceptibility testing methods in terms of the antimicrobial drugs that can be examined. The procedure is placing paper disks saturated with antimicrobial agents on a lawn of bacteria sown on the surface of an agar medium, incubating the plate overnight, and determining the presence or absence of an inhibition zone surrounding the disks. Even though automated antimicrobial systems are now widely used in many clinical microbiology laboratories, the disk diffusion method remains in use because it delivers reliable qualitative results to guide antibiotic therapy in a variety of illnesses. Accurate and reproducible results can be produced by strictly adhering to the approach, using high-quality reagents (culture media and antibiotic-containing disks), and ensuring proper quality control.

The approach works by allowing a predetermined amount of an antimicrobial agent contained in a paper disk or tablet to diffuse across the surface of an agar plate that has already been infected with a standardized microorganism inoculum. As the drug diffuses, it generates a concentration gradient, resulting in the establishment of inhibition zones where the concentration is high enough to prevent the growth of the injected bacterium.²⁰ When tested against Gram negative *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Gram positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* synthesized compounds' **3** antibacterial activity revealed that the majority of them had good

activity. *Escherichia coli* is a facultative anaerobic bacillus that is Gram-negative, often motile, and does not form spores. For every pathotype, there are comparable treatment approaches. Fluid replenishment is the cornerstone of treatment for traveler's diarrhea; antimicrobials and antimotility drugs are used as adjuncts if needed. If the diarrhea is interfering with the trip plan or is moderate to severe, antibiotics may be prescribed.²¹ Opportunistic bacteria called *Klebsiella* are responsible for a variety of extraintestinal diseases. There has been an increase in *Klebsiella* species infections, especially in hospitals where multidrug-resistant forms of the infection have been found.²²

C. FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 4: Biological activities of novel isoxazolidine

P. aeruginosa is a common bacterium that may survive in a variety of settings. It not only harms plants and animals but also people, leading to serious infections in cancer patients with impaired immune systems, those with severe burn injuries, and people with cystic fibrosis.²³ Numerous diseases, such as minor skin infections and wound infections following surgery, can be brought on by *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.²⁴

Agar was used to test the antibacterial activity of the produced isoxazolidine compound **3** against four bacterial strains for 48 hours at 25°C (Table 2). Bacteria thrived on agar plates with a dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solution containing 25 milligrams of the substance.^{25,26} Figure 3 shows that 100 µl dilutions of isoxazolidine compound **3** are effective against gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (20 mm) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (16 mm), as well as gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* (30 mm), *Klebsiella oxytoca* (28 mm) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (26 mm).

TABLE III
Organisms and values of (3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

SL.NO	ORGANISM NAME	GRAM POSITIVE OR NEGATIVE BACTERIA	STANDARD DISC	TEST	DILUTION
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gram negative	AK-25mm	30mm	100µl
2	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	Gram negative	AK-25mm	28mm	100µl
3	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Gram negative	AK-25mm	26mm	100µl
4	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Gram positive	AK-25mm	20mm	100µl
5	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	Gram positive	AK-25mm	16mm	100µl

B. Data Analysis

3. Spectral data of (3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenyl-4-styrylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

¹H NMR: δ 3.39 (1H, ddd, *J* = 7.0, 4.4, 4.1 Hz), 4.73 (1H, d, *J* = 7.0 Hz), 5.26 (1H, d, *J* = 4.4 Hz), 5.73 (1H, dd, *J* = 10.2, 4.1 Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, *J* = 3.4, 1.2 Hz), 6.24 (dd, *J* = 3.4, 1.8 Hz)), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* = 10.2 Hz), 7.00-7.48 (11H, 7.06 (tt, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz), 7.08 (dtd, *J* = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5 Hz), 7.19 (tt, *J* = 7.7, 1.3 Hz), 7.32 (dddd, *J* = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5 Hz), 7.33 (dddd, *J* = 7.7, 7.6, 1.8, 0.5 Hz), 7.39 (dd, *J* = 1.8, 1.2 Hz), 7.42 (dddd, *J* = 7.6, 1.8, 1.3, 0.5 Hz)), 7.49-7.73 (3H, 7.57 (dddd, *J* = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5 Hz), 7.67 (tt, *J* = 7.4, 1.5 Hz)), 7.97 (2H, dddd, *J* = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5 Hz). ¹³C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 127.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (3C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5-128.7 (6C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 129.0 (2C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 132.2 (1C, s), 134.8 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

a. Spectral data of (3-(furan-2-yl)-4-(4-nitrostyryl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 3.47 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.6, 4.4$ Hz), 4.78 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 5.32 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz)), 6.61 (1H, d, $J = 15.8$ Hz), 6.81 (1H, dd, $J = 15.8, 4.6$ Hz), 7.00-7.14 (3H, 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.08 (dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz)), 7.25-7.44 (3H, 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz)), 7.49-7.73 (5H, 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.56 (ddd, $J = 8.6, 1.7, 0.5$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz)), 7.90-8.13 (4H, 7.97 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz), 8.07 (ddd, $J = 8.6, 1.9, 0.5$ Hz)). ^{13}C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 123.8 (2C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.3 (2C, s), 128.5-128.7 (4C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 129.0 (2C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 132.2 (1C, s), 134.8 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 147.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

b. Spectral data of (3-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-methylstyryl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 2.19 (3H, s), 3.39 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.4, 4.1$ Hz), 4.65 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 5.00 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz)), 6.41-6.64 (2H, 6.49 (dd, $J = 16.9, 4.1$ Hz), 6.57 (d, $J = 16.9$ Hz)), 7.00-7.45 (10H, 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.08 (dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz), 7.09 (td, $J = 7.8, 1.2$ Hz), 7.14 (td, $J = 7.7, 2.2$ Hz), 7.16 (ddd, $J = 7.8, 2.2, 0.5$ Hz), 7.26 (ddd, $J = 7.7, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz), 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz)), 7.49-7.73 (3H, 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz)), 7.97 (2H, dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz). ^{13}C NMR: δ 19.4 (1C, s), 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.3 (1C, s), 128.5-128.7 (6C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 129.0 (2C, s), 129.4 (1C, s), 129.8 (1C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 135.4 (1C, s), 136.6 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

c. Spectral data of (4-(2-fluorostyryl)-3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 3.37 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.4, 4.1$ Hz), 4.60 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 5.08 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz)), 6.42-6.59 (2H, 6.49 (dd, $J = 15.7, 4.1$ Hz), 6.52 (d, $J = 15.7$ Hz)), 6.93-7.14 (5H, 7.00 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 7.4, 1.6$ Hz), 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.07 (ddd, $J = 8.3, 1.6, 0.5$ Hz), 7.08 (dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz)), 7.25-7.48 (4H, 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.41 (ddd, $J = 8.3, 7.4, 1.4$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz)), 7.49-7.73 (4H, 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.57 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz)), 7.97 (2H, dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz). ^{13}C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 115.4 (1C, s), 121.3 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.3 (1C, s), 128.5-128.7 (6C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 129.0 (2C, s), 129.4 (1C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 160.6 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

d. Spectral data of (4-(4-chlorostyryl)-3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 3.38 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.4, 4.1$ Hz), 4.65 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 5.09 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz)), 6.41-6.63 (2H, 6.48 (dd, $J = 16.9, 4.1$ Hz), 6.56 (d, $J = 16.9$ Hz)), 7.00-7.14 (3H, 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.08 (dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz)), 7.20-7.73 (10H, 7.26 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 1.8, 0.5$ Hz), 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz), 7.45 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz), 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz)), 7.97 (2H, dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz). ^{13}C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.3 (2C, s), 128.5-128.7 (4C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 128.8-129.1 (4C, 128.9 (s), 129.0 (s)), 131.9 (1C, s), 132.2 (1C, s), 134.1 (1C, s), 134.8 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

e. Spectral data of (4-(2-bromo-4-chlorostyryl)-3-(furan-2-yl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 3.37 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.4, 4.1$ Hz), 4.60 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 4.99 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.30 (2H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz)), 6.38-6.54 (2H, 6.45 (d, $J = 16.7$ Hz), 6.47 (dd, $J = 16.7, 4.1$ Hz)), 6.97-7.45 (9H, 7.03 (dd, $J = 8.3, 0.5$ Hz), 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.08

(dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz), 7.20 (dd, $J = 8.3, 1.7$ Hz), 7.29 (dd, $J = 1.7, 0.5$ Hz), 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz), 7.49-7.73 (3H, 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz), 7.97 (2H, dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz). ^{13}C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 122.6 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5-128.7 (4C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 128.8-129.1 (4C, 128.8 (s), 128.9 (s), 129.0 (s)), 129.4 (1C, s), 131.3 (1C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 133.1 (1C, s), 136.3 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

f. Spectral data of (3-(furan-2-yl)-4-(4-hydroxy-2-methoxystyryl)-2-phenylisoxazolidin-5-yl)(phenyl)methanone

^1H NMR: δ 3.36 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.0, 4.4, 4.2$ Hz), 3.81 (3H, s), 4.54 (1H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz), 4.91 (1H, d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 6.17-6.59 (5H, 6.22 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.2$ Hz), 6.24 (dd, $J = 3.4, 1.8$ Hz), 6.34 (dd, $J = 16.8, 4.2$ Hz), 6.42 (d, $J = 16.8$ Hz), 6.54 (dd, $J = 2.6, 0.4$ Hz)), 6.77 (1H, dd, $J = 8.3, 2.6$ Hz), 7.00-7.14 (3H, 7.06 (tt, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz), 7.08 (dtd, $J = 8.2, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz)), 7.25-7.44 (3H, 7.32 (dddd, $J = 8.2, 8.1, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.39 (dd, $J = 1.8, 1.2$ Hz)), 7.49-7.73 (4H, 7.57 (dddd, $J = 8.4, 7.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.62 (dd, $J = 8.3, 0.4$ Hz), 7.67 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.5$ Hz)), 7.97 (2H, dddd, $J = 8.4, 1.9, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz). ^{13}C NMR: δ 54.2 (1C, s), 55.9 (1C, s), 71.1 (1C, s), 83.1 (1C, s), 99.1 (1C, s), 109.6 (1C, s), 111.5 (1C, s), 115.5 (1C, s), 123.7 (1C, s), 124.3 (2C, s), 128.0-128.2 (2C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5-128.7 (4C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 128.8 (1C, s), 129.0 (2C, s), 129.4 (1C, s), 131.9 (1C, s), 137.0 (1C, s), 143.3 (1C, s), 148.0 (1C, s), 151.0 (1C, s), 157.6 (1C, s), 158.6 (1C, s), 201.5 (1C, s).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the aforementioned work, we have verified that the (1,3-DC) reaction yielded a novel isoxazolidine compound of outstanding vintage and established a generic approach that can be applied to the synthesis of furfuraldehyde nitron, such as highly substituted different chalcone. This review shows that microwave irradiation successfully boosts 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions, which leads to greater yields and shorter reaction times. Analysis has also been done to confirm the chalcone substituent impact. Antimicrobial investigations and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra have validated the development of the unique isoxazolidine structure and the state of the compound confirmed by PXRD.

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